

CLASS DISTRIBUTION MANAGEMENT WITH C ++ BASED ON CODEBLOCK

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ABSTRACT

The problem that occurs when the class division is the difference in the ability of students to have an impact on the ineffectiveness of the ongoing learning process. Student grouping is very important in order to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process. In this study the programming language used is C ++ with the codeblock tool. The results of this study are class division using codeblock-based C ++ programming language more efficiently and effectively.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The campus is a place where there is an interactive teaching and learning process between lecturers and students with a burden according to the level of education (D3 / S1). To support the occurrence of good interaction in the lecture process, a place of study is needed to support the absorption of material well, so that the University's vision and mission are achieved in relation to the quality of education.

To improve the quality of education, an effective teaching and learning process is developed, the quality of students, teachers and lecturers. Various ways have been done to improve the quality of teaching and learning, namely by providing facilities, adding teaching staff, improving the quality of teaching staff and scheduled class distribution. Because with that all the learning process can run smoothly. Scheduled class distribution is also important to do. Usually the class distribution is based on the Student Identification Number.

1.2 Formulation of the problem

Based on the paradigm described above, a problem can be formulated, namely how to manage the division of lecture classes well which can support the quality of education.

1.3 Objectives and Benefits

- a. To fulfill the tasks of Algorithm & Programming Odd Semester Courses and implement Algorithm & Programming Courses
- b. Makes it easy for the student administration section to divide the class well.
- c. Inform the reader how to divide the lecture class

2. LITERATURE

2.1 Related research

There are several studies on predictions of graduation or achievement by using various models / methods as analysis based on historical data:

Budi setiyono and R. Rizal Isnanto, 2008 “Distribution of College Student Classes Using *Fuzzy C-Means Method* “.

The allocation of students into certain classes based on the level of mastery of a course is expected to help students to understand and master more quickly to understand and master a subject learned because it is facilitated and guided by the appropriate instructor.

Risma Uly Manula, 2008 “Analysis and Design of Lecture Room Management Systems at Christian Universities ”.

This system can already be implemented in the Indonesian Christian University in presenting data or information on room use, so that it can provide information on the use of space to the leadership and related units quickly, precisely and accurately. If this system design is implemented in UKI as an educational institution: it will save costs, because the room is used optimally.

Gede Aditra Pradnyana and Agus Aan Jiwa Permana, 2017 “Design of Student Lecture Class Distribution System with K-Means and K-Nearst Neighbors Combination Method ”.

Evaluation is done by observing process time, comparing manual calculations with calculations by the system, as well as evaluating the quality of class lectures (clusters) generated through the calculation of the Silhouette Index (SI). SI is used to validate a data, a single cluster, or even a whole cluster. This method is often used to validate clusters that combine cohesion and separation values.

2.1 Theoretical

Management is the art and science of recording, organizing, compiling, directing, supervising human resources to achieve the stated goals.

C ++ language is an object-oriented programming language to solve problems. Code :: Blocks is a free, non-profit, open source and cross-platform integrated development environment program. (Andy Prasetyo, 2018)

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The stages in this reaserch are as follows:

- a) Data collection
- b) Initial data processing
- c) Grouping
- d) Stages of the proposed method
- e) Experiments and model testing
- f) Research evaluation and validation
- g) Results of research accuracy

The method proposed in this study is a codeblock-based division algorithm to divide class lectures for students. Following are the steps in this study.

1. Calculating the number of students who are there
2. Calculating the number of rooms
3. Calculating the number of courses
4. Calculate the number of classes by dividing 25 number of students
5. Calculate credit / day by dividing the number of courses and the number of spaces then multiplied by the number of classes

The following is the course flow of the program:

Flowchart System

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data used in this study were data from Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic. Following are the steps to calculate the class division of lectures using manual calculation:

A. Calculate the number of classes

Number Of Classes : 25

$$114 / 25$$

B. Calculating Credit Of Poin/Day

1. $(jlmakul : Jmlruang) * jmlkls$

$$(11 : 5) * 5 =$$

The following is a lecture class management program

```
#include <iostream>
using namespace std;
int main()
{
    double jmlmhs, jmlruang, jmlmakul;
    int jmlkelas, pengruang;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "" <sss< endl;
    cout << "PROGRAM PEMBAGIAN RUANG KELAS PERKULIAHAN" << endl;
    cout << "        Teknik Informatika Politeknik Purbaya" << endl;
    cout << "===== " << endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "        Masukkan Jumlah Total Mahasiswa : ";cin >>jmlmhs;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "        Masukkan Jumlah Ruang        : ";cin >>jmlruang;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "        Masukkan Jumlah Makul        : ";cin >>jmlmakul;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    jmlkelas=jmlmhs/25;
    pengruang=(jmlmakul/jmlruang)*jmlkelas;
    cout << "        Total Jumlah Kelas        : "<<jmlkelas << " Kelas" <<endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "        Penggunaan Ruang (dalam 1 hari) : "<<pengruang<< " SKS/Hari"
<<endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    return 0;
}
```

The following are the compiling results from the lecture class division management program using codeblock by running the program and then entering the total number of students, the number of spaces and the number of courses.


```
PROGRAM PEMBAGIAN RUANG KELAS PERKULIAHAN
Teknik Informatika Politeknik Purbaya
=====
Masukkan Jumlah Total Mahasiswa : 114
Masukkan Jumlah Ruang           : 5
Masukkan Jumlah Makul            : 11

Total Jumlah Kelas                : 4 Kelas
Penggunaan Ruang <dalam 1 hari> : 8 SKS/Hari

Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 56.147 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Compyling program results

The calculation carried out saw the total number of students, the number of rooms and the number of courses obtained in total there were 4 classes and space usage in 1 day 8 credits / day.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above research, we obtained a way to manage the division of lecture classes with codeblock-based C ++ in calculating effective, good class lecture distribution and supporting the quality of education.

To get a more effective and better division result you can add a decissionary algorithm.

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